

Settlements in the Late Medieval Ramgarh, Jharkhand

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Abstract

This work is based on the archaeological remains found from the different places in the Ramgarh district of Jharkhand. It is noted that late medieval period for some unknown reasons the king Dalel Singh shifted his capital from Badam to Ramgarh and probably named it after his father Ram Singh. According to a local legend king Dalel Singh excavated a tank beside the double storied *pancharatna* siva temple which was also probably built by him and donated for the *bona-fide* of his draught affected tenants. An exploration has been done by the present authors to find out the residence of the king mentioned in the literature and the temple and tank. After a scientific and systemic survey, two ruined forts and a broken two storied *pancharatna* temple have found. Both the evidences clearly indicate that in the Late Medieval Period for some unknown reasons the king Dalel Singh shifted his capital from Badam to Ramgarh in around 1670s CE and probably named it after his father Ram Singh. Throughout the article, an effort, has been made to reconstruct a comprehensive view on the Late Medieval history and archaeology of the district of Ramgarh.

Key Words: Ramgarh, Kaitha, Fort, Temple, Structure, Chota Nagpur

Introduction

Ramgarh district is one of the 24 districts in the Indian state of Jharkhand, was made on 12 September 2007. It was carved out of erstwhile Hazaribagh District. Ramgarh lies at the heart of the Jharkhand State. The district covers an area of 1,360.08 square kilometres (525.13 sq mi) with a population of 949,159, and a population density of 684 inhabitants per square kilometre . The present boundary of Ramgarh district is in North – Hazaribagh district , South – Rānchidistrict, East – Bokaro and Purulia district of West Bengal and West - Ranchi district. The district headquarter is at Ramgarh town. It is situated on the National Highway 33, 46 km away from state's capital, Ranchion Northern side and 52 km away from Hazaribagh on southern side. Out of the total area, 487.93 Sq. km is covered by forest. Ramgarh district has 315 revenue villages of which 305 is Chiragi and 10 is be-Chiragi.

The district is a part of Chota Nagpur plateau. Important physiographic region of the district is Damodar Trough or Upper Damodar basin or simply Damodar Valley. Major area of the district comes under Damodar Valley. Damodar Valley is bounded by Hazaribagh Plateau in north and Ranchi Plateau in south. Ranchi and Hazaribagh plateau is separated by east-west running Damodar Valley. Barka Pahar (Marang Buru) 1,049 m (3,442 ft) high above sea level located along the Ramgarh- Ranchi border is probably the highest peak, and it also separates the districts. Damodar is the main river of the district and it also forms a major river basin, comprising a number of tributaries amongst them are: Naikari, Bhervi or Bhera and Bokaro river.

Lack of the archaeological exploration, ancient and medieval history of this region is still unknown. Though, from this district, by the effort of A. Ghosh of the University of Calcutta, a few Lower Palaeolithic tools have come to light beside the river Damodar (Sinha and Singha Roy 2018, 28). Some specimens were also found in situ in a thick secondary laterite deposit in the vicinity of Ramgarh town. The district is also rich in the occurrence of the Megalithic tombs in the form of Dolmen and Menhir. Among the places from where megalithic tombs have been reported mentioned may be made of Dulmi; Gola; Kujjukala; Rajrappa; Bhalugram; Jaynagar; Godatu; Huhuwa; Honhe; Bhenpur; Chitarpur; and Bankheta (Sinha and Sinha Roy 2018, 76). The written history of this district is unknown, and no such attempt has been taken to uncover this part of the history, some of the legends are well known which will be discussed later. Same as early history, the late History and the history of the early and late medieval period of this district is vague and quite unclear. E. Lister had given a list of names of the rulers with a short description of their regime before the advance of the British. But, no such attempt has been done by the Archaeology Department to expose material evidences supporting late medieval literature.

According to the District Census Report the word “Ram” is derived from Murram and “Gaḍh ” is derived from Beluagadha but there is no certain evidence to support the view. The report again (Census of India 2011, 5) mentions that Chota Nagpur was the jurisdiction of gigantic king Jarasandha and probably the region was also under subordination of Mahapadmananda of Magadha and Nanda Ugrasena(Census of India 2011, 5). It is also said that entire Chota Nagpur

was under sub-ordination of Asoka the Great, but no such evidence has found to specify this postulation.

The written history of this place is known from the late medieval period, when certain evidence is found about the residence of the Chief of Ramgarh for a hundred years, after Badam was abandoned in 1670s. Ramgarh was attacked and captured by the Muhammadans under Hidayat Ali Khan in 1740, but the complete subjugation of the district was cut short by necessity of moving away to meet a Maratha invasion of Bihar. It was again captured in 1772 by a British expedition under the command of Lieutenant Goddard, who replaced Makund Singh by Tej Singh as the chief of Ramgarh. Makund Singh fled, and shortly after died, as did his infant son. Tej Singh established himself at Ichak, and the former capital quickly fell into decay.

Therefore, the literature evidence is strongly support that the place, Ramgarh, was ruled directly by a few independent chiefs of the Ramgarh Family in the late medieval period. They are;

- I. Dalel Singh with a *fauzdar* (Thakur) Golal Singh (1667-1724 CE)
- II. Maharudar Singh with a *fauzdar* Manir Singh (Probably a few months in 1724 CE)
- III. Bishan Singh (1724-63)
- IV. Puratan Singh (Probably a few months in 1763)
- V. Makund Singh with a *fauzdar* Tej Singh (1763-72)

Actually, the family was started with the hand of Bagdeo Singh (1368-1402) and his elder brother Singdoo probably the Rajputs of Bundelkhand (Lister 1917, 55). Bagdeo Singh was more auspicious than his elder brother and quarrelled with the King of Nagpur Raj. He defeated Kapper Deo, the Raja of the Karanpura area under the Maharaja of Nagvnsi King, and captured 22 parganas. Therefore, he declared himself as an independent ruler and settled his capital at Urda. He positioned his elder brother, Singdoo, in the rank of the height officer, i.e., *fauzdar* or Thakur. The tradition had been continuing since that time. The descendants of Bagdeo Singh were always taking the charge as a chief with a *fauzdar* or Thakur from the descendants of Singdoo. The Family shifted their capital at Ramgarh in around 1660s under the chieftain of Dalel Singh (1667-1724 CE). Ramgarh was served as a capital upto the year of 1772 when *fauzdar* or Thakur Tej Singh revolted against his Chieftain Makund Singh. He, with the help of British Army overthrow Makund Singh and declared himself as a chief of the Ramgarh Family. Therefore, he shifted his capital from Ramgarh to Ichak.

Remains of Late Medieval Archaeology

Literary evidences indicate that in between 1670 to 1772 the place Ramgarh was probably used as the capital of a few provincial chiefs of Ramgarh family and it was deserted when the provincial capital was established at the Ichak. Now, if the place was used as the provincial capital than there might have a place for the residence of the local chief and other structure in their daily life that must be existed in form of materials remains or intact in present days.

An archaeological exploration has been conducted to find out if any such remains have been existed. And after exploration three places have been identified, i.e., Kila Mandir in the heart of the present city of the Ramgarh, Raja Garh/Garh Bandh, on a hill at the northern end of the present town, and Kaitha, a superb of the Ramgarh town, with ruined forts and a brick built temple respectively (Figure 1).

Figure 1 Showing the location of the Kila Mandir (Temple Complex at Ramgarh town), Raja Garh, and the Kaitha Brick Temple

Kila Mandir (230 37/ 37// N; 850 30/ 59// E)

Located at the heart of the town 1.56 km south of the river of the Damodar (Figure 1) with a height of approximately 8-10 m from the surrounding surface. The area which has now existed in the form of a mound extends from south-east to north-west is 109 m and from north-east to south-west is 115 m. In the middle of the mound a complex of three modern temples is constructed with a huge boundary wall. Local people known the place as the fort of the king but nothing is left, except a few remains. Outside of the present temple's boundary wall remains of brick structures and stone wall are found. And the surface of the mound except the temple area covers with bricks butts and block of stones. To the east and the south-east of the present temple a wall made of small square stone blocks jointed each other's by clay and plastered with thick mortar is seemed (Figure 2A and B). The thickness of the wall is not known as the present temple wall is constructed over the ancient wall. The wall is broken and now 130 cm from the surface is standing. The wall can be seen on the east-south-east- and south of the present temple complex. The stone wall is oriented from north-south and takes a turn after 45 m from the north towards west. After running 25 m towards west the wall is finished and did not found in any other side. To the south, and south-west of the present temple a few parts of the brick structure have been noted with the brick size of the 23x 21x7.5 cm (Figure 3). 35m east of the long stone wall and around the high mound a deep ditch with approximately a depth of 7-8 feet have been noted (Figure 4) except the norther portion of the mound where the ditch was filled with the modern people to make a road for approaching the present temple complex. To the south-western corner beside the ditch below the surface from 3 feet a few pieces of iron slags have been discovered (Figure 3).

Figure 2A: A complete Layout of the ancient fort based on the materials remains

Figure 2B: Remains of the ancient stone walls which has been discovered during the time

Figure 3 Remains of two circular brick structure on the north-eastern and southern corner and evidence of iron slag on the south-west corner of the mound

Brick Temple at Kaitha ($23^{\circ} 38' 11''$ N; $85^{\circ} 33' 21''$ E):

Beside the ruined fort other two remains of the late medieval period has been traced out from this district. One is from Kaithā , a small village in the fringe of the Ramgarh town, approximately 3.66 km east from the town and 1.82 km west from the river Damodar and 450 m east from the NH 23. The temple is unique in its nature. It has a two storied building. The ground floor is square in plan with two entrances on the north and south directions respectively. The outer wall is thick in nature and made of bricks with a mortar plaster. After the entrance a circumambulatory path is seen around a square but solid structure (Figure 8). The solid square structure is also made of the same bricks used to build the outer wall with a thick lime plaster. It will not be possible to know why the square chamber would have been built as there is no such way to access into the chamber. Probably it has served as a support on which the upper storey is standing in balance. The circumambulatory path is also square in nature with a square chamber attached two doors at each corner of the structure (Figure 5). On the eastern side of the structure a hall is seemed projected towards the east with a thick wall. This part was projected in a purpose to build the staircase for approaching into the first floor . The plan of the first floor is totally different from the ground floor . On the first floor , at the centre , a rectangular sanctum is seen with an Śiva Liṅga in the middle and an entrance to the east . After the entrance of the sanctum a four pillared small hall is seen (Figure 6) which is still used a *Ghogamandapa* (Figure 8). A porch is seen attached with the pillared hall which is open. And toward the eastern end of the porch the entrance of the temple is made which can be approached after passed through nineteen high staircases. The porch is used as a place where dances and songs are performed during the time of worship. Around the sanctum and the pillared hall, a square circumambulatory path is made - exactly over the circumambulatory path on the ground floor (Figure 8). At each corner of the circumambulatory path a four arched doors canopy is seen with a conical shaped dome on the top (Figure 6).

Over the sanctum of the temple a cone shaped tower (*ekaratna*) made of bricks with a lime plaster is seen (Figure 8). The tower is *saptaratha* in nature and the top of the structure is like a dome. Over each of the canopy which is described above a conical shaped tower is also noted, and same like the big tower in the centre these small towers are also domal in shape at the top (Figure 7).

The entrance to the first floor of the temple is also interesting. It contains two arched doors. And over each of the doors a conical shaped tower is placed with the same domal top (Figure 8).

Ground Plan (Ground Floor)

R.F.: 1:1 Ground Plan (First Floor)

Figure 5 Ground plan of the Ground Floor on the Temple at Kaithā

Figure 6 Ground Plan of the First Floor of the Temple at Kaithā

A

B

Figure 7 The Brick temple at Kaithā

A

B

C

D

Figure 8 A. Circumambulatory path around the sanctum of the First Floor; B. Entrance into the First Floor; C. A general view of the Porch and Small Hall; D. Circumambulatory path around the solid square chamber in the ground floor

Raja Garh/ Garh Bandh

Locally known as Raja Garh or Garh Bandh, situated on a small upland (tilla) at the northern end of the modern town of Ramgarh beside the river Damador (Figure 9). The hill is oval in size with a size of 322 m long and 174 m wide. On the eastern side of the hill remain of a fort is found. Outer wall which is square in nature with a size of 111 x 100 m made of block of stones and plastered with a thick layer mortar (Figure 10). Inside this square outer stone wall foundation of three blocks of square big rooms have been traced out (Figure 11). The three square rooms are big and more or less same less in nature. Outer walls of these rooms are made of block of stones, but inner walls of these rooms made of small bricks with a size of 15 x 18x 4 cm. except the three rooms, foundation of a wall is also found to the northern end of the outer stone wall. To the western side of the fort complex the land is plain and also square in nature. Probably, this part of the *tilla* was designed for a big ground. The Ground plan of the fort is not determined properly due to thick forest which covered the hill completely and also served as a den of wild animals. But scattered brick butts over the surface indicate that a few super structures were once built within the square stone wall. Same as the Kila Mandir local people considered this place as the fort of the King of the Ramgarh Family.

Figure 8 Location of the Raja Garh or Garh Bandh

Figure 9 Remains of the fort; Green outline showing the outer stone wall of the fort; red lines indicates square chambers with their respective walls

Figure 10 Remains of the fort; Green outline showing the outer stone wall of the fort; red lines indicates square chambers with their respective walls

General Observation

The aforementioned details on the literature and archaeological remains gave an impetus in the field of the late medieval archaeology and history of the district Ramgarh. Now, some facts are still not being clear and need to deal with care. A systematic excavation of the forts areas can unveil certain evidences. Therefore, all the present commands are tentative and we hope precise facts will be exposed by the hand of future generation. However, it would be safe to postulate an observation rather than any certain conclusion on the history and archaeology of the Late Medieval Ramgarh:

- I. It is now more or less confirmed that the place, for the first time, ruled directly or more to say served as a capital in the Late Medieval Period by the hand of the Ramgarh family.
- II. Two forts, rather called “A Fort Complex”, were constructed by the independent King Dalel Singh in around 1670s and probably named as ““Ramgarh” before the name of his father and former King Ram Singh. This postulation is only based on the assumption that the name “Ramgarh” is not found in any literature in the Early Historic Period or Early Medieval Period and it could be possible that the King who founded the fort complex was named it after his father to commemorate him.
- III. Distance between the two forts is 1.3 km and their purpose of use is still vague. In between the two forts present Ramgarh town is situated and find out any archaeological remains in between these two forts areas is quite unbearable. It should be mentioned here that both of the forts are situated on a *Tilla* or natural uplands as well as the temple is two storied, but only the upper storey is used as secret place. It would also not be clear why a raised platform was needed. It was probably due to the river Damodar but present nature of the river in this area is quite undisturbed and gentle. However, in this regards, more important to reveal why two forts were constructed instated a big one? The fort found on the Kila Mandir is well planned with a moat and strong outer wall. Another fort beside the river is only strengthened by a stone outer wall. Based on the plans of both of the forts, it can be said that the fort on the Kila Mandir was more important than the fort beside the river. It could be possible that the well planned fort, i.e., Kila Mandir, might have been served as a residence of an important person, probably used as the residence of the King and on the other hand the fort beside the river could have been used as the residence of the higher officers or *fauzdar* of Thakur. It also can be said that forts are built only for the royal persons or officers and common people probably inhabited in between the two forts areas. These assumptions only inveterate after systematic excavations in the two forts areas and a few places in between the two forts.
- IV. The unique brick temple at Kaitha with the combination of *pancharatna* and *ekbanla* architectural style, though not sophisticated like which are found in the present geographical area in West Bengal, is no doubt built sometime in the late medieval period. Probably due to the lack of experience the local artist could have not been successful to shape it in the form of typical *pancharatna* temple style and gave it a shape of double storied building with a big *ratna* combined with other four small cylindrical *ratnas*. Construction materials and architectural style clearly indicate that

this temple was built sometime in the Late Medieval period. However, no such indicators are available which could help us to ascertain this temple in a certain period and in the name of a ruler. But a legend is quite popular among the local people that this temple is made by the king Dalel Sing after a famine with a big Tank. We found a big tank attached to this temple, but no archaeological remains are also there to correlate this tank with the temple.

After all, we have done nothing except carefully noted the late medieval history of the region which is found from the literature and systematically analysis the scatters archaeological remains in an around the present Ramgarh town. Both the evidences clearly indicate that in the Late Medieval Period for some unknown reasons the king Dalel Singh shifted his capital from Badam to Ramgarh in around 1670s CE and probably named it after his father Ram Singh. He also excavated a tank beside the double storied *pancharatna* siva temple which was probably built by him and donated for the *bona-fide* of his draught affected tenants.

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